

Hydrobiological studies on Savikeri pond with reference to physico-chemical parameters and zooplankton diversity.

PRABHU GOLLAR AND GIRISH G. KADADEVARU*

Department of Zoology, Karnatak University, Dharwad, Karnataka, India

E-mail: tigrisp43@gmail.com, kadadevarug@gmail.com

*Author for correspondence

Abstract

The study was undertaken to assess the physico-chemical conditions and record the zooplankton diversity at Savikeri pond in Haveri district. Savikeri pond is one of the oldest manmade ponds, rain water is the only source of water for this pond. This pond is used for domestic utility by people of Savikeri. A total 21 species recorded here. Rotifer was the dominating group in this pond with 7 species. *Keratella tropica* was the most abundant species in this group. The physical and chemical factors like temperature, pH, Transparency, conductivity, TDS, alkalinity, Chlorides, hardness, free carbon dioxide and DO were estimated.

Key words: Zooplankton diversity, physico-chemical parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Water is nature's most wonderful, most essential and an invaluable gift to man, which not only keeps him alive by meeting the basic necessities of the smallest living unit, the cells, but also provides inexhaustible reserve of food to him. Without water, there would not be life of any kind on the earth. It is one of the basic necessities along with air. Man has used fresh water from the earliest time. At first only for drinking; cooking etc. Later growth of population, rising standard of living and advancement of technology in the last two centuries has proved the ever-increasing utility of water. According to Coulton and Mrak (1997) the sources of water supply in general, may be classified as follows

- 1) Surface water:** Contains dissolved salts, mostly from the biotic influences. It is in the form of inland lakes, rivers and streams. Of the total global water, it forms approximately 0.017%
- 2) Ground water:** This appears to be clearer because of percolation through the soil but it contains more of dissolved salts. It amounts to 0.625% of the total global water
- 3) Sea water:** supposed to be the most impure form of waters, contains a lot of dissolved salts. Most of the global water is sea water (97.2%).
- 4) Polar ice and glaciers:** Usually it is in the solid form and is supposed to be in pure condition. This accounts for 2.15% of the global water. Of the natural elements, water is considered to be of prime importance to the existence of man, plants and animals. It also plays an essential role in agriculture, industries, pisciculture, forestry, and navigation.

Ponds have tendency to become thermally stratified during summer and winter to undergo definite seasonal periodicity in depth distribution of heat and oxygen. Light too penetrates only to a certain depth, depending upon turbidity. These gradations of oxygen, light and temperature profoundly influence life in the pond, its distribution and adaptations. In India the total water available for use is about 1900 cubic meters. Of this, about 86% is in the form of rivers, streams, lakes and ponds. Karnataka is one of the agriculturally and industrially leading states in India. Industrial effluents, treated or untreated, are dumped into natural water bodies causing irreparable damage to the aquatic biota. Karnataka state is known for its large number of water bodies like small impoundments and bigger tanks which are mainly used for irrigation, fisheries, washing, bathing, etc. Such water bodies are subjected to disturbances like domestic waste discharge, cattle-bathing, human fecal contamination etc. The Dharma Reservoir project is an existing medium irrigation project on river Dharma in Uttara Kannada district. Uttara Kannada district is located in the western part of India and it is a part of central Western Ghats.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Study Area

Savikeri pond is one of the oldest manmade ponds, situated at Savikeri village of Hangal taluk, Haveri district. Which falls 75°04'35" E longitude and 14°42'35" N latitude. Rain water is the only source of water for this pond (Fig 1). The data were taken on monthly from August, 2019 to February, 2020. The water spread area of the pond is 1.3 Km². The length of the pond is 750m and the maximum depth of the pond is 3 m. This pond is used for domestic utility by people of Savikeri.

Fig- 1

2.2 Sample collection and analysis

For the analysis of physico-chemical factors the water sample was collected at regular interval of one month for a period of six months (August, 2019 to February, 2020) from Dharma reservoir. Collection of samples were made early morning between 6 am – 9 am. For qualitative analysis of zooplankton, water samples were collected by standard plankton net made of nylon blotting cloth silk net(68µm). plankton net had 30cm diameter at one end, tapers at another end. Zooplankton sample were collected by sieving 100 liters of water through net for quantitative estimation. Samples were collected in bottles adding formaldehyde and glycerin.

Electric conductivity, pH, TDS and Salinity were recorded with the help of a multi parameter PCSTestr 35, great for water. This laboratory multi parameter Testr features long-life pH electrode with a wide sample compatibility. Pin-style conductivity sensors feature stainless steel electrode for chemical resistance and durability. Atmospheric temperature and Water temperature were also recorded with the help of probe. Humidity was recorded with the help of Hygrometer. Water transparency was recorded with the help of Secchi disc. DO (dissolved oxygen), CO₂ (free carbon dioxide), total hardness, chlorides were analyzed titrimetrically (APHA AWWA publication).

3. Result:

3.1 Abiotic factors

The Atmospheric temperature was recorded at Savikeri pond during the collection of samples. It was recorded highest in the month of January, 2020 with 25°C and lowest in the month of December, 2019 with 20°C. The average atmospheric temperature during study period was 18.57°C. The water temperature of Savikeri pond, it was recorded highest in the month of November, 2019 with 27°C and lowest in the month of December, 2019 with 25°C. The average water temperature during the study period was 25.71°C. The pH was maximum with 7.9 in the month of January, 2020 and lowest in the month of August, 2019 with 7.34. The average pH of the Savikeri pond during the study period was 7.60. The humidity was recorded highest in the month of August, 2019 having 74% and recoded lowest with 65% in the month of January, 2020. The average humidity of the Savikeri pond during the study period was 68.57% (Table 1).

Electric conductivity was maximum in the month of January, 2020 with 259mS/m and minimum in the month of August, 2019 having 11.32mS/m. The average conductivity was 187.46 mS/m. Total dissolved solids (TDS) was recorded maximum in the month of January, 2020 with 184ppm and minimum in the month of August, 2019 with 80.4ppm. The average TDS during the study period was 141.2ppm. Salinity was recorded maximum in the month of January, 2020 with 134ppm and recorded lowest in the month of August, 2019 with 57.8 ppm. The average salinity was 101.84 ppm. transparency was recorded maximum in the month of October, 2019 with 70cm and minimum in the month of January, 2020 with 60cm. The average transparency was 63.42cm. Dissolved oxygen in was maximum in the month of February, 2020 having 13.2mg/l and minimum in the month of November, 2019 having 3.32mg/l. The average DO during the study period was 6.6mg/l. Free carbon dioxide is constant in all months, the value was 0.66 mg/l. The average Free carbon dioxide content was 0.66mg/l. Total hardness of Savikeri pond was maximum in the month of January, 2020

with 107.2mg/l and minimum in the month of November, 2019 with 28mg/l. The average total hardness was 70.73mg/l. Chloride content was maximum in the month of February, 2020 with 29.63mg/l and minimum in November, 2019 with 12.61 mg/l. The average value of chloride during the study period was 17.84mg/l. Total alkalinity was maximum in the month of February, 2020 with 46mg/l and minimum in August, 2019 with 16mg/l. The average value was 27.42mg/l (Table 2)

3.2 Biotic factors:

In Savikeri pond, 21 species of zoo-planktons (fig 2) were recorded consisting of 7 Cladocers, 6 Copepods, 8 Rotifers. Species richness was in the month of August, 2019 and it was minimum during September, 2019. The most abundant species among Cladocera – *Moinamicrura*, *Tropocyclops prasinus* was the most abundant Copepod. Amongst the Rotifera – *Keratella tropica* is leading species (Table 3).

Table 1 Monthly average of physico-chemical properties of Savikeri pond

MON THS	At Temp, °C	Water Temp, °C	pH	Humidity, %	Conductivity, mS/m	TDS, ppm	Salinity, ppm	Transparency, cm	DO, mg/l	Free CO ₂ , mg/l	Hardness, mg/l	Chlorides, mg/l	Alkalinity, mg/l
AUG 2019	21°C	25°C	7.34	74%	11.32	80.4	57.8	68cm	5.32	0.66	50.6	22.152	16
SEP	22°C	25°C	7.56	65%	187.1	127	86.9	66cm	6	0.66	72	13.61	20
OCT	21°C	26°C	7.7	69%	196.3	138	95.7	70cm	5.04	0.66	86.6	13.31	20
NOV	21°C	27°C	7.4	70%	174.5	124	91.5	60cm	3.32	0.66	28	12.61	30
DEC	20°C	25°C	7.52	69%	228	162	117	60cm	6.92	0.66	80	16.618	30
JAN2020	25°C	26°C	7.9	68%	259	184	134	60cm	6.4	0.66	107.2	17.018	30
FEB	21°C	26°C	7.8	65%	256	173	130	60cm	13.2	0.66	106.1	29.63	46

Table 2 List of zooplankton species recorded in the Savikeri pond during the study period.

GROUP	FAMILY	GENUS
CLADOCERA (07)	<i>Sididae</i>	<i>Daphnia</i>
		<i>Diaphanosoma</i>
	<i>Daphnidae</i>	<i>Ceriodaphnia</i>
	<i>Moinidae</i>	<i>Moina</i>
	<i>Chydoridae</i>	<i>Chydorus</i>
	<i>Aloninae</i>	<i>Alona</i>
COPEPOD (06)	<i>Diaptomidae</i>	<i>Heliodiaptomus</i>
		<i>Neodiaptomus</i>
	<i>Cyclopoidae</i>	<i>Tropocyclops</i>
		<i>Mesocyclops</i>
ROTIFER (08)	<i>Brachionidae</i>	<i>Brachionus</i>
		<i>Keratella</i>
	<i>Filinidae</i>	<i>Filinia</i>

Table 3 Monthly variations of Zooplanktons at Savikeri pond.

PLANKTONS	AUG	SEP	OCT	DEC
CLADOCERA				
<i>Daphnia carinata</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Moina micrura</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Moina brachiata</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Diaphanosoma sarsi</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Ceriodaphnia cornuta</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Chydorus reticulatus</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Alona polchella</i>	-	-	+	-
Total	5	0	3	0
COPEPODA				
<i>Tropocyclops prasinus</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Heliodyptomus viduus</i>	+	+	-	+
<i>Mesocyclops hyalinus</i>	+	+	-	-
<i>Mesocyclops leukarti</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Neodiptomus strigilipes</i>	+	-	-	+
<i>Thermocyclops hyalinus</i>	+	-	-	-
Total	6	3	1	3
ROTIFERA				
<i>Brachionus diversicornis</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>Brachionus caudatus</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>Brachionus calyciflorus</i>	-	+	-	-
<i>Keratella tropica</i>	-	+	+	+
<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>	-	+	+	+
<i>Keratella serrulata</i>	-	-	-	+
<i>Filinia opoliensis</i>	-	-	+	-
<i>Brachionus falcatus</i>	+	-	-	-
Total	1	3	3	5

4. Discussion

The pH of Savikeri pond ranged from 7.34 to 7.9. It is quite possible that when organic matter is more the aerobic bacterial degeneration will also be more which results in the release of carbon dioxide reducing pH. The humidity ranged between 74% to 68%. It was recorded highest in the month of August, 2019. electric conductivity is ranging between 11.32 to 259 mS/m. total dissolved solids (TDS) was ranged between 80.4 ppm to 184ppm. Its Salinity was ranged between 57.8 ppm to 134 ppm (Table -1). It was recorded maximum in the month of January, 2020 and recorded lowest in the month of August, 2019. In the present investigation, the higher values of transparency were observed in Savikeri pond during January, 2020 and higher in October, 2019. may be due to shallow ness of pond with higher anthropogenic disturbance which cause higher turbidity. Monthly variation in DO at Savikeri pond reveal that in pond, the oxygen level was 3.32 mg/l to 13.2mg/l. Do was increased in February, 2019 because pollution from fertilizer runoff and poorly treated waste water from Savikeri village. free carbon di-oxide having constant value in all months, the value having 0.66 mg/l. In the present study Savikeri pond showed high levels of hardness. The increase in hardness was coupled with the increase in the calcium concentration which suggests that calcium is one of the factors contributing to the hardness. In the present study showed high levels of hardness. The increase in hardness was coupled with the increase in the calcium concentration which suggests that calcium is one of the factors contributing to the hardness. The lakes near the shore line receive significantly inputs of chlorides by atmospheric transport from the seas. In fresh waters the manifold increase in chlorides may be largely due to industrial sources municipal waste waters, irrigation drainage. Total alkalinity of Savikeri pond varied from 16 to 46 mg/l. Most of the alkalinity in natural waters is formed due to dissolution of carbon-di-oxide in water. Total alkalinity of Savikeri pond varied from 16 to 46 mg/l. Most of the alkalinity in natural waters is formed due to dissolution of carbon-di-oxide in water

In the present study 7 Cladoceran species belonging to 4 families are recorded from Savikeri pond, which account 24% of total Zooplankton group. *Daphnia carinata* and *Diaphanosoma sarsi* of family sididae and *Moina micrura* and *Moina brachiata* from family Moinidae and *Ceriodaphnia cornuta* from family Daphnidae are recorded during study period *Ceriodaphnia cornuta* was the most frequently observed cladoceran in the present day. Family Chydoridae was represented with 1 species, *Chydorus reticulatus* In addition *Diaphanosoma sarsi* of family sididae and *Moina micrura* from family Moinidae are recorded during study period *Moina micrura* was the most frequently observed cladoceran in the present day. *Heliodiaptomus viduus* and *Neodiaptomus strigilipes*. In Cyclopoidae Family, 4 species, *Tropocyclops prasinus*, *Mesocyclops hyalinus*, *Mesocyclops leuckarti* and *Thermocyclops hyalinus* were recorded during the study period *Tropocyclops prasinus* was the most frequently observed Copepod in the study period. In the present study 8 species were recorded from Savikeri pond, which account 36% of total Zooplankton group. Family Brachionidae was represented with 7 species, *Brachionus calyciflorus*, *Brachionus falcatus*, *Brachionus diversicornis*, *Brachionus caudatus*, *Keratella tropica*, *Keratella cochlearis* and *Keratella serruleta*. In Filinidae family 1 species, *Filinia opoliensis* were recorded during study period. *Keratella tropica* was the most frequently observed Rotifer in the study period.

Conclusion:

A total of two water bodies were investigated for monthly variation of physicochemical and Zooplankton composition, the Savikeri pond had low dissolved oxygen content. The pH values are normal to, Atmospheric temperature, water temperature, Humidity, conductivity, CO₂ content, Hardness, chloride content and alkalinity levels were high. Hardness level in Savikeri pond is very high and the water in the pond can be designated as very hard. Zooplankton diversity studied for a period of 4 months revealed that the diversity is rich with 25 species of Zooplanktons. The species composition also shows monthly variations. However, further studies are required to understand the population dynamics and to evaluate the trophic status of the water body based on the Zooplanktons. The present investigation shows Savikeri pond had lower of DO and other parameters like CO₂, Alkalinity, and Chloride, Hardness in the pond are in the higher range suggesting the immediate attention to prevent the further pollution of the pond. However, the water quality of Dharma reservoir is still quite suitable. If the habitats have to be preserved for their intended use, sustainable and holistic management measure for the remediation of the tanks are an immediate necessity. However, if the habitats have to be preserved for their intended use, continuous monitoring is essential. In addition, sustainable and holistic management measures are necessary for the conservation of water bodies. As there is no single piece of legislation, which comprehensively addresses the problem of eutrophication of fresh water bodies, it is strongly recommend to the concerned authorities of the city municipality to facilitate the proper management and recycling of the effluents and sewage, and subjecting the tanks to least anthropogenic activities.

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